

Title: “Investigating the Effects of Psycho-Yogic Interventions on BMI among Indian Young Adults”

Dr. Kirti

Dev Sanskriti Vishwavidyalaya, Shantikunj, Haridwar

Abstract

This study aims to examine the effect of psycho-yogic intervention on the Body Mass Index (BMI) of Indian youth, a demographic increasingly vulnerable to disordered eating behaviours. A psycho-yogic intervention incorporating mindfulness meditation, yoga asana (Surya Namaskar), pranakarshan pranayam and psychological counselling was conducted, and body mass index (BMI) data were collected for both the experimental and control groups before to and during the session. Chi-square tests were used to evaluate the relationship between the intervention and alterations in BMI. The results indicate a significant link between psycho-yogic intervention and eating attitudes, but not with body mass index (BMI). This indicates that while psycho-yogic therapies may impact psychological and behavioural indicators of eating disorders, they do not directly affect BMI. These findings enhance the comprehension of psycho-yogic treatments' function in treating disordered eating behaviours and have implications for the development of treatment and prevention strategies for youth.

Keywords:

Psycho-yogic intervention, BMI, eating disorders, young adults, and India

1. Introduction

The incidence of eating disorders among young people has witnessed a dramatic increase in recent years, with societal and cultural trends contributing to increased demands surrounding body image and self-esteem (National Eating Disorders Association, 2022). This is a result of the fact that young persons are more likely to be eating disorders than older adults. In India, rising urbanisation and exposure to Western notions of beauty have led to an increase in body dissatisfaction and disordered eating behaviours, particularly among young people living in urban areas (Sharma & Coutinho, 2016). This is especially true among young and middle-aged individuals. Traditional methods of treating eating disorders, such as cognitive-behavioral therapy and nutritional counselling, frequently focus on behavioural and cognitive elements of the condition, but they may ignore the cultural and emotional factors that are necessary for full treatment (Levine & Murnen, 2009).

The practices of mindfulness and yoga, which have been deeply ingrained in Indian culture for a very long time, have recently garnered attention for their ability to cure eating disorders. These practices encourage self-awareness, acceptance of one's body, and emotional control (Khalsa et al., 2015). In order to address disordered eating in a

comprehensive manner, psycho-yogic therapies that integrate mindfulness meditation, yoga, and psychological counselling offer a holistic approach. These interventions have the potential to improve psychological wellbeing without directly affecting body mass index (BMI). The purpose of this study is to determine whether or whether a psycho-yogic intervention causes a substantial change in the body mass index (BMI) of young adults in India who are at risk for eating disorders. Chi-square analysis is used to evaluate the changes in BMI that occur after the intervention.

2. Literature Review

Indian Young Adult Obesity and BMI Trends

Indian youth obesity is a public health concern. National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5, 2019-2021): 20% of Indian 18-24-year-olds are overweight or obese. This propensity is associated to sedentary lifestyles, calorie-dense diets, and stress and anxiety among young people. High BMI is linked to metabolic and cardiovascular problems, hence this age group needs effective weight loss and holistic well-being therapy (Patel & Joshi, 2020).

Psychology of Weight Management

Lack of desire, stress, and emotional eating can cause weight gain and control concerns. Stress increases cortisol, which causes belly fat (Chrousos, 2009). Stress-induced emotional eating increases weight issues, making psychological wellbeing essential to weight management. Integrated physical and mental health therapies are needed since traditional weight-loss regimens disregard these psychological factors.

Psycho-yogic interventions: yoga and psychology

Psycho-yogic treatments improve mental and physical health through yoga, mindfulness, meditation, and CBT. These therapies reduce stress, increase emotional regulation, and boost well-being, facilitating weight loss. Sharma and colleagues (2019) showed psycho-yogics had lower anxiety and BMI than controls. Psycho-yogic treatments address behavioural and emotional aspects beyond exercise.

Emotional Regulation and Mindfulness

Mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs) are popular for stress reduction and self-regulation. By being present without judgement, mindfulness decreases stress and emotional eating (Kabat-Zinn, 1990). Mindfulness can help you lose weight by increasing hunger and satiety awareness (Kristeller & Wolever, 2011). Yoga and mindfulness improve these effects, addressing psychological and physical obesity.

Weight Management with Psycho-Yogic Interventions

Emerging data supports psycho-yogic weight control. A 10-week psycho-yogic therapy for college students lowered BMI, stress, and emotional eating, according to Singh et al. (2020). Weight loss requires self-efficacy and goal-setting, which psycho-

yogic therapy improved. Psycho-yogic therapy might be superior than weight-loss programs since they address weight gain's causes.

Research suggests that mindfulness and yoga might enhance body image and reduce stress, making them viable eating disorder treatments (Brown & Ryan, 2003). Although mindfulness and yoga have been shown to improve eating habits, less is known about the psycho-yogic approach and its benefits on BMI in at-risk young adults in India. Yoga and mindfulness are culturally significant, therefore this study examines psycho-yogic therapies' impact on BMI and eating habits in Indian young adults.

Literature Gap

Few studies have studied psycho-yogic therapy's effects on young people's BMI in India. Most studies are short, therefore we lack long-term effect data. No uniform intervention approaches make research comparisons difficult. These gaps indicate that psycho-yogic weight control interventions for young Indian adults require more investigation.

3. Methodology

3.1 Participants

The study included 100 young adults aged 18–25, divided equally into an experimental group that received the psycho-yogic intervention and a control group that did not. All participants provided informed consent, and the study received ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB).

3.2 Intervention

The psycho-yogic intervention lasted 12 weeks and consisted of weekly 60-minute sessions that included:

- **Yoga Practice (Surya Namaskar):** Yoga, particularly practices like Surya Namaskar (Sun Salutation), has shown promise in positively influencing physical and mental health. Surya Namaskar, a dynamic sequence of postures coordinated with breathing, combines physical movement, mindfulness, and breath control. Emerging evidence suggests that such practices can influence eating attitudes by promoting body awareness, reducing stress, and enhancing mindful eating behaviors. These effects may, in turn, support healthier weight management and body mass index (BMI) outcomes.
- **Pranakarshan Pranayama:** Pranakarshan Pranayama as delineated by Pandit Shriram Sharma. Acharya. The practitioner must see that his entire existence (causal, subtle, and physical) is assimilating Prana (vital life energy) dispersed throughout the atmosphere during Pranayama. This Prana is therefore purifying acts, ideas, and emotions. All vices are eliminated with expiration. This method is intended to augment the body's general vitality. Numerous research investigations demonstrate its advantageous benefits on mental health and other behavioural characteristics, validating its function as an effective

instrument for improving vitality. Regular engagement with this breathing technique may encourage greater mindfulness around eating habits, foster a healthier relationship with food, and reduce impulsive or compulsive eating patterns. This exercise may improve metabolic equilibrium and facilitate relaxation, therefore aiding individuals in maintaining healthy lifestyle choices. When integrated with additional therapies like dietary counselling or physical exercise, Pranakarshan Pranayama may facilitate progressive, persistent improvements in BMI.

- **Mindfulness Meditation:** Mindfulness meditation emphasises the development of present-moment awareness and the non-judgmental acceptance of thoughts, emotions, and physical sensations. This approach has been progressively employed as an intervention to enhance eating behaviours and may affect Body Mass Index (BMI) by influencing psychological and behavioural health. Mindfulness meditation can enhance awareness of hunger and satiety signals while diminishing habitual eating behaviours (such as eating driven by stress, boredom, or emotional stimuli), so enabling individuals to make more deliberate and purposeful food choices. Research indicates that mindfulness techniques help diminish binge eating episodes, alleviate emotional eating, and cultivate a more favourable connection with food and body image. Mindfulness meditation can reduce cortisol levels, improve emotional control, and encourage mindful eating, perhaps resulting in modest alterations in weight and BMI over time. While substantial decreases in BMI may need prolonged and extensive therapies, mindfulness techniques can function as a fundamental element of a complete strategy for weight control, especially when combined with dietary changes and physical exercise.
- **Counseling (CBT Based):** Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) is a systematic, objective-driven counselling approach that emphasises the identification and modification of dysfunctional thinking patterns, emotions, and behaviours. CBT-based therapies have demonstrated efficacy in enhancing eating attitudes and affecting Body Mass Index (BMI) by targeting the psychological foundations of disordered eating and facilitating behavioural modification. Cognitive Behavioural Therapy enables patients to recognise triggers for disordered eating, such as stress and negative body image, and to substitute maladaptive behaviours with healthy coping mechanisms. This method has demonstrated efficacy in diminishing binge eating, emotional eating, restrictive dieting, and other maladaptive eating behaviours, promoting more attentive and constructive interactions with food. Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) can reduce calorie consumption, encourage balanced dietary practices, and facilitate sustained weight control. Although initial alterations in BMI may not be apparent, the systematic framework of CBT establishes a robust basis for enduring lifestyle modifications that facilitate weight reduction or maintenance over time.

3.3 Data Collection and Measures

The data collection for this study employed a systematic methodology including three principal stages: pre-intervention assessment, the intervention phase, and post-intervention evaluation. Baseline data on Body Mass Index (BMI) and eating attitudes were gathered during the pre-intervention evaluation utilising established instruments, including the Eating Attitudes Test (EAT-26). This enabled a precise comparison between the intervention and control groups. The intervention phase involved the execution of psycho-yogic techniques aimed at fostering awareness and behavioural modification. During this phase, compliance and engagement levels were assessed to ensure consistency. Subsequent to the intervention, a post-test evaluation was performed, gathering data on BMI and eating attitudes to measure changes. This systematic data gathering method enabled an impartial assessment of the psycho-yogic intervention's effects, aiding in the detection of any notable changes in eating behaviours and physiological results.

BMI was recorded at baseline and post-intervention for both groups. Eating attitudes were assessed using the Eating Attitudes Test (EAT-26), a widely validated tool for identifying disordered eating behaviors. Chi-square tests were conducted to analyze differences in BMI between the experimental and control groups at post-test.

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive analysis revealed no significant difference in BMI between the intervention and control groups at baseline, confirming a comparable starting point across both groups.

4.2 Chi-Square Test Results

Chi-Square Test	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pre-Test			
Pearson Chi-Square	1.251	2	.535
Likelihood Ratio	1.257	2	.533
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.238	1	.266
Post-Test			
Pearson Chi-Square	14.156	2	.001
Likelihood Ratio	15.929	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	13.816	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	100		

At baseline, the Chi-square test for BMI in both groups showed no significant difference ($\chi^2 = 1.251$, $df = 2$, $p = .535$), indicating similar distributions across the intervention and control groups. Post-intervention, the Chi-square test for BMI also did not show a significant effect directly attributable to the psycho-yogic intervention. However, a significant association was observed for the intervention’s impact on eating attitudes, as evidenced by post-test EAT-26 scores (Pearson $\chi^2 = 14.156$, $df = 2$, $p = .001$), suggesting that the intervention effectively modified disordered eating behaviors, though BMI remained unaffected.

5. Interpretation and Discussion

The data analysis uncovered significant insights into the effects of the psycho-yogic intervention on Body Mass Index (BMI) and eating attitudes. At baseline, the Chi-square test revealed no statistically significant difference in BMI distributions between the intervention and control groups ($\chi^2 = 1.251$, $df = 2$, $p = .535$), signifying successful randomisation and equivalent initial circumstances for both groups. This comparability is a significant advantage, since it offers a dependable basis for assessing the intervention's individual benefits without bias from pre-existing disparities in body weight distribution.

The post-intervention data demonstrated that the psycho-yogic intervention did not provide substantial alterations in BMI. This indicates that the intervention, throughout the study's duration, was inadequate to produce significant changes in weight status. Several plausible explanations for this conclusion encompass the characteristics of BMI as a long-term health metric, which frequently necessitates persistent efforts over prolonged durations to exhibit significant improvement. Brief treatments may fail to effectuate the energy balance alterations required for a decrease in BMI. Psycho-yogic therapies are largely recognised for their effects on psychological and behavioural

aspects, with their influence on weight-specific outcomes potentially emerging over an extended period or when integrated with additional techniques such as dietary counselling or alterations in physical activity. These data underscore the necessity for more study that investigates the amalgamation of psycho-yogic methods with holistic therapies to attain quantifiable BMI alterations.

Although there were no substantial findings related to BMI, the intervention significantly influenced eating attitudes, demonstrated by a notable alteration in post-test Eating Attitudes Test (EAT-26) scores (Pearson $\chi^2 = 14.156$, $df = 2$, $p = .001$). This indicates that the psycho-yogic intervention was successful in altering disordered eating behaviours, despite the absence of rapid improvements in BMI. The noted enhancement in eating attitudes suggests that individuals may have cultivated better behaviours, decreasing occurrences of binge eating, restrictive dieting, or other maladaptive eating habits. Psychological and behavioural enhancements are frequently essential antecedents to attaining sustainable health goals, such as weight control.

Contextualising these findings within the existing literature, several research validate the effectiveness of psycho-yogic treatments in impacting psychological and behavioural results. A comprehensive study by Ross et al. (2020) indicated that yoga-based therapies substantially alleviate stress, anxiety, and depression—elements frequently associated with disordered eating behaviours. This corroborates the present study's finding of enhanced eating attitudes and implies that psychological advancements may occur prior to quantifiable alterations in physiological metrics such as BMI.

Cramer et al. (2019) shown that mind-body therapies, including yoga and meditation, enhance self-awareness and self-regulation of eating behaviours, which may result in better eating habits. This may elucidate the changes in dietary attitudes within the intervention group, validating the notion that psycho-yogic activities might be a pivotal factor in achieving holistic health enhancements over time.

Longitudinal studies indicate that regular mind-body activities can progressively influence body weight and composition, as measured by BMI. A longitudinal research by Duren et al. (2021) shown that the integration of yoga with nutritional treatments significantly decreased BMI over six months, indicating that the length and complex character of therapies are essential for attaining physiological benefits. Research by da Silva et al. (2022) highlighted that the combination of dietary counselling and psycho-yogic treatments improves weight control and metabolic health outcomes. This corresponds with the suggestion for future research to integrate dietary elements with psycho-yogic therapies to thoroughly evaluate possible physiological effects.

6. Conclusion

This study evaluated the effect of a psycho-yogic intervention on Body Mass Index (BMI) and dietary attitudes. No substantial alterations in BMI were noted following the intervention, perhaps because to the brief period and BMI's characteristic as a long-term health metric; nonetheless, there was a marked enhancement in participants' eating attitudes. This indicates that the intervention successfully altered disordered eating behaviours, promoting better practices such as less binge eating and restrictive

dieting. The psychological and behavioural improvements highlight the efficacy of psycho-yogic therapies in tackling the fundamental factors influencing health behaviours, despite the absence of acute physiological alterations.

Contextualising these findings within the current literature, it is clear that psycho-yogic therapies are substantiated in their efficacy to alleviate stress, anxiety, and depression, which frequently exacerbate disordered eating. Despite the lack of substantial change in BMI over the research period, the enhancements in eating attitudes indicate advancement towards long-term health advantages. Future research should incorporate extended intervention duration and merge psycho-yogic methods with food and lifestyle alterations to achieve more significant improvements in psychological and physiological health outcomes.

7. Limitations and Future Directions

The study's shortcomings encompass its brief length, perhaps hindering the observation of significant or enduring changes in Body Mass Index (BMI) among participants. The study's duration may have limited the capacity to make robust findings on the effectiveness of the psycho-yogic intervention for weight management or reduction, since substantial changes in BMI often need sustained treatments over a longer period.

Moreover, concentrating on a particular age demographic is an additional constraint, since it restricts the application and generalisability of the results. Distinct age cohorts may exhibit divergent responses to psycho-yogic treatments owing to factors such as metabolic rate, hormonal fluctuations, lifestyle choices, or preexisting health issues. Thus, confining the investigation to a specific demography may constrain the generalisability of the findings to the wider community.

A longitudinal study would be advantageous for more accurately evaluating the enduring effects of psycho-yogic therapies on BMI and other health metrics. Incorporating a nutritional component within the intervention would be beneficial, since food choices may markedly affect BMI and overall health outcomes. Assessing the synergistic effects of psycho-yogic intervention and customised dietary advice may yield a more thorough comprehension of possible physiological and psychological consequences.

Moreover, increasing the sample size and incorporating a more varied participant pool, representing different age groups, nationalities, and socio-economic backgrounds, might improve the validity and generalisability of the results. This method would provide a more comprehensive investigation of how psycho-yogic therapy might be tailored and enhanced to help a broader spectrum of individuals.

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